

Conclusion. Final Assessment Integrating realistic resources and real-life events into foreign language instruction for high school students improves their linguistic abilities, cultural comprehension, and confidence in practical communication. Despite existing challenges, strategic planning and the use of suitable resources can surmount these obstacles, guaranteeing a comprehensive and stimulating learning experience. By connecting classroom instruction with practical application, educators may provide students with the necessary tools for success in a progressively networked society.

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APPLYING MODERN APPROACHES TO FL LEARNING PRACTISES OF PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS

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Annotation. Through this article, the author describes in detail current approaches and techniques of teaching foreign languages in primary school

settings by providing examples for practices, such as, gamification of the process through interactive ways.

Keywords. *Language Acquisition, Developing Skills, Communication, Games, Gamification, Language System.*

Introduction. The most fundamental and positive changes in modern primary education is the decree of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 10, 2012 “On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages” is Resolution No. PQ-1875 [1]. On the basis of this decision, learning foreign languages, mainly English, from the 1st grade of general secondary schools in the form of game-based lessons and oral speech lessons, and from the 2nd grade, the alphabet, reading and grammar teaching begins step by step. According to the decision, under the leadership of the Coordinating Council, which is constantly working on the further development of the study of foreign languages, an incomparable scale of work was started in all directions of the educational field. For example, since the 2013-2014 school year, ongoing teaching of foreign languages in the form of game-style exercises and oral speech lessons has been started in the first grades of secondary schools. Also, textbooks and teaching-methodical sets for these classes were created. It is worth noting that the games in the complexes created for the first grades are proportional to the age of the children. Children began their first experience with a foreign language by learning the culture of greetings, colors and common words in the form of a dialogue [2].

Main body. Undoubtedly, equipping the foreign language rooms in the educational institutions of our country with modern information and communication technologies and advanced technical means of teaching, broadcasting programs and broadcasts on TV and radio channels that teach children and teenagers foreign languages, the history of other countries and regular screening of popular foreign art and multimedia films dedicated to culture, world

science and technical news with Uzbek subtitles allowed our young people to get to know the past, culture and science of humanity around the world.

When teaching foreign languages to students in primary grades, especially in the first grade, it is necessary to take into account the age, physiology and psychological characteristics of the student [3]. As noted in the decision, the implementation of foreign language teaching through gamifying the lessons and oral speech lessons in the first grades is rather appropriate for younger students. The use of game technologies in education is one of the most effective tools. During the game, their knowledge, outlook, and thinking will expand. Scientists believe that the game approach to education facilitates the learning process. It not only makes it easier, but also increases the enthusiasm to this subject and encourages the child to acquire deep knowledge. Game-style lessons help children develop their communication skills. First graders get engrossed in different visuals with pictures or videos. Games should be regularly used to develop their speech through different colored pictures [4]. For example, What is this?, Who is this?, Who knows the most words?. it is necessary to encourage children to remember words and pronounce them correctly. Depending on the growth of children's vocabulary, it is important to organize other types of games and various competitions. At first, children can perform exercises on topics such as "Fruit Names", "Occupations", "Home Appliances" with the help of games. Then, if they are shown in a harmonious state to the colorful images on the computer, the pupils' speech will develop and the circle of attitude to the environment will expand. During the presentation phase of the new topic, words and pictures will appear on the screen. Students will be able to listen to the words and pronounce them. It is necessary to pay attention to the principle of individualization of education when presenting the subject with the help of a computer. Some students find it difficult to accept the graphic image of the word, and some have difficulty with the sound image. The computer solves this difficulty by means of exercises, helps find the aspects of the student who are in trouble with mastering the language [5].

Conclusion

To sum up, it is really critical to start foreign language teaching and learning from early stages of life, especially, in primary schools. The reason for that, children can build a base for they themselves in this period, since they can easily focus on a single thing. In order to boost their language skills, as most school teachers, it is highly recommended to apply modern approaches to motivate the pupils to learn more and more.

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THE EFFECTIVE WAYS OF USING AN ART OF SPEAKING IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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***Annotation.** This article about a mix of perseverance, patience, and practice to improve speaking abilities. Through accepting mistakes, increasing vocabulary, overcoming hesitancy, enhancing pronunciation, and engaging in group*